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Universal Energy Access, Agricultural Growth, and Sustainable Land Use: Zambia’s Policy Roadmap to 2050

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Summary

This technical brief argues for the need of integrated land, energy and water resource use planning for achieving the Zambia National Energy Compact’s ambitious targets of domestic production of maize, wheat and soybean. By using the CLEWs modelling framework, we show that the least-cost pathway for achieving the targets includes the mechanization of agriculture, with rainfed and irrigated commercial-scale farming respectively covering 24.7% and 19.8% of the abovementioned crops’ total harvested area by 2050. This increases the pressure on groundwater resources (up to more than 1000% increased use) and the need for electricity for pumping (up to 0.85 GW by 2050), highlighting the need for infrastructure planning and for diversification of the primary supply. Solar PV can be a low-cost option for supporting the electrification of irrigation, while contributing to the Integrated Resource Plan’s targets of 33% non-hydro renewable electricity supply by 2050.

Key recommendations:

- *Create coordinated support* for investments in mechanization of agriculture, extension of electricity access to farms, and surface-based irrigation, to achieve the ambitious targets of increased wheat, maize and soybean production.
- *Support the upscaling of distributed solar PV* as a low-cost enabler of increased small-scale agriculture productivity and resilience to droughts.
- *Deploy utility scale PV to 4.27 GW by 2030* by 2030 as least-cost option to contribute, alongside onshore wind, to the IRP’s target for non-hydro renewable electricity supply, considering its use for both bulk electricity supply and distributed electrification of farming.

1. Introduction

The electricity demand for agriculture in Zambia is projected to grow from 1,200 MW in 2030 to 3,625 MW by 2050, driven by ambitious goals of increased production of wheat, maize, and soybean output. This trajectory underscores the urgent need to align energy planning with agricultural growth, as outlined in the [National Energy Compact](#) the [Integrated Resource Plan \(IRP\)](#), and the [8th National Development Plan](#).

[https://www.fao.org/energy/projects/project-details/bioenergy-and-food-security-\(befs\)-assessment-and-capacity-building-for-zambia/en](https://www.fao.org/energy/projects/project-details/bioenergy-and-food-security-(befs)-assessment-and-capacity-building-for-zambia/en)

Yet, expanding agriculture and energy access will also reshape Zambia’s land use patterns. Large-scale irrigation, renewable energy installations, and agro-energy zones will require careful spatial planning to balance competing demands for farmland, forests, mining, and conservation areas. Integrating

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land use considerations into energy–agriculture strategies is therefore essential to ensure that expansion supports food security, climate resilience, and sustainable resource management. This calls for alignment with the [National Land Policy](#) under the Ministry of Lands and Natural Resources, which provides the framework for equitable land allocation, tenure security, and sustainable land management.

Achieving universal access to electricity by 2030 will require the accelerated deployment of distributed renewable energy (DRE) technologies such as mini-grids, solar home systems, and productive-use applications that complement grid expansion and directly support rural transformation. Anchored in the [National Energy Policy](#), the Rural Electrification Master Plan (REMP), and Zambia’s SDG 7 commitments, decentralized energy systems will be critical to closing the urban–rural access gap while powering households, schools, health centers, and agro-processing enterprises.

At the same time, expanding generation infrastructure to reach 10,000 MW by 2030 is central to Zambia’s energy security and climate resilience strategy, jointly with a diversification of the low-carbon generation portfolio. The National Energy Compact sets a target share of non-hydropower renewables of 33% by 2030. Diversifying beyond hydropower through solar, wind, biomass, geothermal, and small hydropower projects will strengthen the resilience to hydrological shocks and stimulate green industrialization. Fast-tracking renewable energy feed-in tariffs, operationalizing a national renewable energy fund, and embedding renewable solutions within agricultural value chains will be essential to achieving this ambition, in line with the National Energy Policy and the IRP. The mobilization of investments may be guided by least-cost planning principles, supported by blended financing frameworks that de-risk private capital and modernize the grid, as emphasized in the [Renewable Energy Strategy and Action Plan](#).

Collectively, these priorities demand stronger coordination across the Ministry of Energy, Ministry of Green Economy and Environment, Ministry of

Agriculture, Ministry of Lands and Natural Resources, Ministry of Water Development and Sanitation, Ministry of Infrastructure, Housing and Urban Development, and Ministry of Local Government and Rural Development, to harmonize policies that link energy access, food security, land use, and climate mitigation and adaptation objectives. Embedding climate resilience and natural resource efficiency into infrastructure investment, alongside integrated monitoring across the IRP, Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs), and the National Adaptation Plan (NAP), will ensure that Zambia advances toward universal access and sustainable energy for all.

2. Addressing the challenges

Zambia faces several critical challenges in reconciling rising agricultural electricity demand (whose share in the national demand is expected to grow from the current 2% to 33% in 2050), universal energy access goals, and the need for climate-resilient generation expansion with sustainable land use management.

First, the projected growth in crop production and rural electrification will intensify the pressure on the energy system, as highlighted in the Integrated Resource Plan, which identifies agriculture, mining, and industrialization as key drivers of future electricity demand.

Second, the current hydropower-dominated mix accounts for more than 80% of generation. However, the World Bank has forecasted that the consecutive number of dry days, with respect to historical values (143 average annual days), might increase by 6 and 9 days, respectively, for the time horizon 2020-2039 and 2040-2059 under a SSP1-2.6 climate change scenario, increasing Zambia’s energy system’s vulnerability to droughts. Progress toward diversifying renewables and embedding them in the agricultural value chains remains slower than the rate of increase of the vulnerabilities, despite targets in the National Energy Policy to expand renewable energy sources and improve resilience.

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Finally, weak institutional coordination across the aforementioned Ministries further undermines coherent planning. Without integrated action, Zambia risks falling short of its commitments to food security, universal access, and low-carbon development, as emphasized in the National Energy Compact and Zambia's [Nationally Determined Contribution](#).

3. Approach and Scenario Development

This study aims to shed light on the resource use implications of the ambitious domestic production targets for three of Zambia's largest crops (wheat, maize and soybean), and how access to distributed non-hydro renewable energy may act as enabler of agricultural development. To this end, it employs the Climate, Land, Energy, and Water systems (CLEWs) modeling framework to analyze Zambia's agricultural transformation and energy transition pathways jointly, under a cost-minimization perspective. CLEWs provides an integrated systems approach that captures the interdependencies between energy demand, agricultural production, land use, and climate resilience. By linking sectoral models, the framework enables coherent policy analysis that reflects trade-offs, synergies, and long-term sustainability outcomes.

Many countries have adopted the CLEWs modelling framework as a decision-support tool. For example, Ethiopia used CLEWs to guide its Climate-Resilient Green Economy Strategy by evaluating trade-offs between hydropower expansion and irrigation. Kenya applied CLEWs to examine synergies between agriculture, energy, and water access in arid regions. In Mauritius, CLEWs supported national planning on water security and renewable energy. At the same time, Nicaragua and the Dominican Republic used CLEWs to balance land-use decisions with forest conservation and biofuel development.

The United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA), KTH Royal Institute of Technology and the University of Zambia jointly ran a UNDESA-funded 1-year program where a large group of analysts from various governmental institutions, research organizations and utilities in Zambia were trained in the use of modelling. The group jointly created CLEWs model infrastructure for Zambia and designed scenarios

to deliver insights on key questions for the country's long-term integrated resource planning.

3.1. Scenario Development

We analyze three questions related to policy priorities brought up by the program participants.

Q1. What implications do the National Energy Compact's 2030 and 2050 targets for crop production have for investment in and planning of land, water and electricity supply in Zambia?

We designed for this the AgriBoost scenario, which implements the domestic production targets of 10 million tons of maize by 2050 (+212% compared to 2023), 3 million tons of soybeans (+349%) and 15 million tons of wheat (+4350%).

Q2. What role can distributed solar PV have in supporting the achievement of the maize, soybean and wheat production targets?

We designed for this the AgriBoostPlus scenario, which stems from the same assumptions as AgriBoost, but it assumes that any increase of irrigation is electrified only via off-grid solar PV panels and assesses the costs of such pathway against the baseline of AgriBoost.

Q3. Can synergies exist between the IRP's target of 33% non-hydro renewables in national electricity supply by 2030 and the enhancement of agricultural production?

The Green_Shift scenario stems from the same assumptions as AgriBoostPlus, and it investigates if solar PV is among the least-cost technological options for increasing the share of non-hydro renewables in national electricity supply to 33% by 2030. This gives insights on whether electrifying irrigation via distributed solar PV may also be an enabler for reaching the IRP's non-hydro generation targets and, vice versa, whether the latter targets may create a more favorable environment for investments in solar PV in the agricultural sector.

3.2 Analytical Framework

Integrated Systems Optimisation. CLEWs links electricity generation, agricultural output, land use change, and water supply, allowing the cross-sectoral impacts of sectoral policies to be quantified under a least-cost perspective, while taking into account resource constraints. One key methodological choice was to separate the land area of the country into 3 agro-ecological zones, based on the average crop yields. This allows an optimal reallocation of agricultural land also across zones, based on actual yields and costs of production.

Policy Alignment. The scenarios are benchmarked against Zambia’s Integrated Resource Plan (IRP 2023-2053), National Energy Policy (2019), 8th National Development Plan, and National Energy Compact (AES 300) to ensure consistency with national targets.

Data Inputs. The key drivers in the model are the projections for electricity, food crops (maize, wheat, soy and cassava) and water commodity demands; the costs of electricity and agricultural production; the policy targets (as per scenario descriptions); and resource constraints (e.g. land availability, runoff and groundwater, primary energy resources). The data for the energy system representation is partly derived from CCG’s Zambia Whole Energy System Model and then updated and calibrated for the reference year of 2023

are provided upon request in annex to this technical note.

4. Policy implications and recommendations

Q1. What implications do the National Energy Compact’s 2030 and 2050 targets for crop production have for investment in and planning of land, water and electricity supply in Zambia?

The increase in crop production assumed in the AgriBoost scenario leads to a larger harvested area in each agro-ecological zone at the expense of grassland, more than quadrupling greenhouse gas emissions from 1.5 MT to 7 MT CO₂eq in cumulative land-use-change emissions from 2023 to 2050 when compared to the reference scenario. The land use expansion, however, is not directly proportional to the production increase. While production by 2050 increases by 73.6%, agricultural land-use change expands by 71.2% due to a shift from small-scale to commercial-scale agriculture and an increase in irrigation, which in turn boosts agricultural yields. The production of wheat, soybean and maize crops moves to a large commercial-scale farming system, with rainfed and irrigated harvested area respectively covering 24.7% and 19.8% of the total by 2050, while small-scale farming is optimized to decrease from 90% of the total harvested area in 2023 to 13.1% by 2050.

Figure 1 Use of water for crop irrigation in the AgriBoost scenario (featuring the National Energy Compact’s production targets for maize, wheat and soybean) vs the Reference scenario (same as the former but without the targets).

based on the latest available update of [Zambia’s installed electricity generation capacity](#) published by the Ministry of Energy. The calibration of land covers and uses, water cycle and agricultural yields stem from GAEZ v4.0 data and national statistics.

The technical description of the model, its boundaries and its structure, its datasets and all the data sources

Figure 1 shows that the increase of maize, wheat and soybean production assumed in the AgriBoost scenario leads to significantly higher water use for agriculture, reaching 4.7 Bm³ by 2050 compared to 0.4 Bm³ in the reference scenario. This water comes primarily from the annual groundwater recharge (under average

precipitation conditions)¹, resulting in proportionately larger electricity consumption for water pumping, particularly in the largest agro-ecological zone (C1). The irrigation mostly supplies the large increase in wheat production (over 40 times in 2050 compared to 2023). Overall, the energy and water requirements increase to respectively around 12 and 13 times those in the reference scenario to achieve productivity boost.

The higher production of wheat, soy, and maize results in a 17% cumulative capital cost increase in the time horizon 2023-2050 and a 22% increase in direct CO_{2eq} emissions. The rise in crop production leads to a total installed power supply capacity of 9.62 GW by 2030 compared to the 9.45 GW of the reference scenario because of the increased energy required for pumping water for irrigation. Medium-scale hydropower combined with utility-scale solar PV emerges as the most cost-effective mix for electricity supply.

Recommendation – Create coordinated (policy and regulatory) support for investments in mechanization, extension of electricity access and surface-based irrigation for both small and commercial scale farms, to achieve the ambitious targets of increased wheat, maize and soybean production. The least-cost path to achieving the targets includes extension of irrigated harvested area (3670% increase) and industrialization of agriculture (700% increase in commercial-scale agriculture), but this increases the pressure on groundwater resources (1246% increased use), currently the most used source of irrigation, and requires electricity that currently is not available to many farms. Failing to account for these cross-sectoral feedbacks will delay the agricultural development and undermine the achievement of the domestic production targets.

Q2. What role can distributed solar PV have in supporting the achievement of the maize, soybean and wheat production targets?

The introduction of distributed solar PV for pumping water in small-scale agriculture reaches 0.37 GW of installed capacity in the AgriBoostPlus scenario (Figure

2), reducing by 4 MW the installed capacity of coal power plants, 0.2% the total CO_{2eq} direct emissions and with a 3% increase in cumulative capital costs over all years compared with the AgriBoost scenario.

Figure 2 Differences in installed capacity and CO_{2eq} emissions between AgriBoost and AgriBoostPlus scenarios.

The increased access to electricity and irrigation carries the potential to mitigate the exposure of small-scale farming to prolonged droughts although it shifts the dependency on water from rainfall towards withdrawals.

Recommendation - Support the upscaling of distributed solar PV as a low-cost enabler to power water pumping for irrigation. The introduction of distributed solar PV cuts the CO_{2eq} direct emissions by 2050 of 0.2% and increases small-scale agriculture’s energy supply resilience to droughts with 3% cumulative capital cost increase over the time horizon 2023-2050.

Q3. Can synergies exist between the IRP’s target of 33% non-hydro renewables in national electricity supply by 2030 and the enhancement of agricultural production?

Achieving the target of 33% non-hydro renewables (GreenShift scenario) reduces the risk of greater resource stress and vulnerability to climate change by reducing the dependence on water. The least-cost electricity mix to reach the target (while considering also the large targeted increase of wheat, maize and soybean production) implies increasing the installed capacity of utility-scale, grid-connected solar PV by 25%,

¹ In the CLEWs model, only the surface water and groundwater recharges from the year’s precipitation can be tapped into. If dry scenarios were modelled, such increase of water withdrawal might become constraining.

distributed solar PV to 260 MW, and onshore wind to 3500 MW by 2030, while reducing by 19% the installed capacity of medium size hydro power (See Figure 3). This enhances the system’s resilience to climate shocks and mitigates land-use-change impacts, leading to a 24% reduction in direct CO_{2eq} emissions by 2050 compared with the AgriBoost scenario. Additionally, it shows that also grid-connected and distributed solar are among the low-cost enablers of increased agricultural production. The faster non-hydro renewable roll-out by 2030 and the adoption of onshore wind reduce the reliance on coal by 26% by 2050 compared to the AgriBoost scenario. Also distributed solar PV upscales to a total of 2.43 GW of installed capacity by 2050. Moreover, as for the AgriBoostPlus scenario, of these 2.43 GW, 370 MW are allocated only for supplying the deployment of small-scale farming, enabling its expansion. Electrifying irrigation via distributed solar PV may thus be seen as a cost-competitive enabler for reaching the IRP’s non-hydro generation targets.

Recommendation – Deploy Utility scale solar PV by 850 MW together with 260 MW of distributed solar PV by 2030 as least-cost option to contribute, alongside onshore wind (3500 MW), to the IRP’s target for non-hydro renewable electricity supply, considering its use for both bulk electricity supply and electrification of farming. Grid-connected and distributed solar PV emerges from this scenario as one of the two lowest-cost non-hydro options for diversifying the supply while

meeting targets of increased agricultural production, considering resource potential and techno-economic characteristics.

6. Final considerations and future steps

According to the IRP, the electrification of the agricultural sector will consist mostly in the industrialization of the whole production chain. The electrification of the water supply for irrigation has a minor impact on the national electricity needs per se, but it bears implications for infrastructure planning. The use of distributed solar PV represents a low-cost alternative for electrifying irrigation for small-scale farming. Future work will look at extending the representation of the agricultural sector in the model to capture all uses of energy and water in the whole production chain (including also livestock and processing of agricultural products). It will also include improving the accuracy of emissions representation through a dedicated GHG inventory, enabling more robust assessment of production-driven impacts. Moreover, coupling the CLEWs model with geospatially explicit electrification models could enhance the representation of the energy system and provide more insights on the respective roles of grid-connected or off-grid solar PV in electrifying agriculture. Finally, further analysis is needed to evaluate the risks associated with expanded groundwater-based irrigation and the resulting resource stress under climate change.

Figure 3 Total installed capacity (GW) across all scenarios.